

MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR DIQQATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALASIDA OLIMLAR FIKRLARI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar diqqatini rivojlantirish masalasida olimlar fikrlari keltirib o'tilgan va tahlil qilingan. Maqola davomida asosli fikr hamda mulohazalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar, diqqatni rivojlantirish, olimlar fikrlari.

OPINIONS OF SCIENTISTS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ATTENTION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Abstract. In this article, the opinions of scientists on the development of preschool children's attention are presented and analyzed. Reasonable opinions and comments are given throughout the article.

Key words: children of preschool age, development of attention, opinions of scientists.

МНЕНИЯ УЧЕНЫХ О РАЗВИТИИ ВНИМАНИЯ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены и проанализированы мнения ученых по вопросу развития внимания дошкольников. Обоснованные мнения и комментарии даны на протяжении всей статьи.

Ключевые слова: дети дошкольного возраста, развитие внимания, мнения ученых.

Diqqat shunday muhim bir psixik jarayonki, u insonning jamiki faoliyatlarida bevosita ishtirok etadi. I.P.Pavlovning¹ oliy nerv faoliyati haqidagi ta'limoti va A.A.Uxtomskiyar tomonidan ilgari surgan dominantlik tamoyili va ularning zamondoshlari tadqiqotlarida diqqatning fiziologik asoslari va mexanizmlarini ilmiy nuqtai nazardan tushuntirish imkonini yaratdi.

Sobiq sovet psixologiyasida diqqat muammosi xorij psixologiyasiga nisbatan ancha murakkab mustaqil ilmiy manbalarga ega hisoblanadi va u shu bilan o'zaro farq qiladi. Sobiq sovet psixologiyasida diqqatga nisbatan mukammal qat'iy fikr vujudga kelgani yo'q, lekin uning atrofida juda ko'p tortishuvlar, munozaralar bo'lib o'tgan. Diqqatning psixologik tabiati to'g'risidagi 20-30 yillarda boshlangan ilmiy bahslar, to hozirgi kungacha davom etib kelmoqda. Ilmiy munozaralarning zamirida asosiy fikr diqqatning bitta ob'ektga qaratilishidir. Bu ilmiy model ong ob'ekt tarzida ifodalanadi. Bu g'oyani yirik psixolog P.P.Blonskiy ilgari surgan va asoslagan. Uning fikricha, odamning ongi bitta ob'ektga qaratilgandan keyin u atrofda narsa va hodisalarni ko'rmaydi.

Ko'pchilik psixologlar P.P.Blonskiyning² bu fikriga qo'shilmaydilar. Jumladan, atoqli psixolog S.L.Rubinshteyn mulohazasiga ko'ra diqqat ongga ham, ob'ektning xususiyatlariga ham bog'liq emas. Buning ahamiyatli tomoni diqqatning ob'ektga yo'naltirilishidir. Mazkur yo'naltirishning asosiy sabablari sifatida shaxs, ehtiyoj, maqsad ko'rsatiladi. Demak, diqqat

¹ Shapovalenko I.V. Vozrastnaya psixologiya (Psixologiya razvitiya i vozrastnaya psixologiya): uchebnik dlya studentov vuzov. Shapovalenko I.V. – M.: Gordariki, 2007. – 344s.

² Bleyxer V.M., Burlachuk L.F. Psixologicheskaya diagnostika intellekta i lichnosti. K., 1978.

odamning munosabati orqali ifodalanadi, ya'ni diqqat - munosabatdir. Bu yerda diqqat psixik jarayon emas, balki shaxs xususiyatini belgilab beryapti.

Diqqat qaralgan tashqi ifodaga ega bo'lgan ob'ektning sezish, idrok qilishdan iboratdir. Shu o'rinda qarama-qarshilik vujudga keladi, chunki ob'ektning yo'qolishi bilan diqqat ham o'z funksiyasini tugatadi.

A.N.Leontev³ mulohazasiga ko'ra, bu orientir faoliyati emas, chunki ob'ektning paydo bo'lishi bilan diqqat ham namoyon bo'ladi, ob'ekt yo'q bo'lsa, demak diqqat ham bo'lmaydi, deb ta'kidlaydi. P.Ya.Galperin esa ob'ektning paydo bo'lishi bilan diqqat yuzaga keladi. Ob'ekt yo'qolgandan keyin esa psixik qism bo'lgan tekshirish, nazorat qilish jarayoni boshlanadi. Demak, diqqat ongning bir ob'ektga yo'naltirilishi va ongli holatni nazorat qiluvchi jarayondan iboratdir. Psixologiyada diqqatni "yo'naltirish" deganda, psixik faoliyatning tanlovchanligi va ixtiyoriy hamda ixtiyorsizligi tushuniladi.

20-yillarda bir qancha psixologlar diqqat muammosini ustanovka bilan bog'lab tushuntirishga harakat qiladilar. Buning yaqqol isboti sifatida K.N.Kornilov tahriri ostida 1926 yilda chop qilingan psixologiya darsligidagi bir mavzu "Ustanovka va diqqat" deb atalganligi bilan izohlash mumkin. Darslikda yozilishicha, qator ob'ektlardan bir ob'ektning ajratish diqqatning sub'ektiv kechinmasidir va buni ob'ektiv hodisalar bilan taqqoslash, sezgi organlarining ustanovkasidan, ishlash vaziyatidan iboratdir.

Shunga o'xshash g'oya L.S.Vigotskiyning dastlabki tadqiqotlarida ham ko'zga tashlanadi. L.S.Vigotskiy diqqat bilan aloqador bo'lgan ikkita ustanovka turini ajratib ko'rsatadi, ular:

- a) sensor ustanovka - tayyorgarlikda idrokning ustunligi qobiliyati
- b) motor ustanovka - tayyorgarlikda harakatning ustunligi qobiliyati.

Sensor ustanovkada idrok, motor ustanovkada esa harakat ustunligi sezilib turadi. L.S.Vigotskiy⁴ unga misol qilib jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotida komanda (buyruq) berishni misol keltiradi. Safda turganlarga qarab "O'ng" deb aytamiz. Shu zahotiy oq saflanganlar buyruq oxirini aytishga sensor ustanovka qo'zg'aydi "ga!" deyish oyoqlarni aylantirishga moslashish bilan bog'liq motor ustanovka komanda oxirini eshitishni ta'minlaydi.

Bu yillarda psixologlar ustanovkani kishining ijtimoiy tajribasi bilan bog'liq ravishda tadqiqot qilishga harakat qilganlar. P.P.Blonskiyning mulohazasicha, diqqatning asosida kishining ijtimoiy qiziqishlari yotadi. Psixologlar orasida diqqatni tushuntirishda turli qarashlar, nazariyalar vujudga keladi. Vaholanki, P.P.Blonskiy diqqat bilan qo'rquv, vahimani bir narsa deb qaraydi. qo'rquv - bu diqqatning intensivroq namoyon bo'lishi, ya'ni maksimal darajada aks etishi deb tushuntiradi. Bu yerda psixik faoliyatning ma'nosi butunlay yo'qotib ko'rsatilgandek tuyuladi va diqqat biologik nuqtai nazardan qaraganga o'xshab ketadi. Biologik pozitsiyada diqqat bosh miya yarim sharlari faoliyati bilan emas, balki vegetativ nerv tizimi bilan bog'liqlikda tushuntiriladi.

Taniqli psixolog D.N.Uznadzening diqqatni ustanovka bilan bog'lash nazariyasiga N.F.Dobrinin qarshi chiqdi. N.F.Dobrinin fikricha, diqqatni ustanovka bilan bog'lovchi nazariya quyidagi jihatlarni hisobga olmagan. Diqqat haqiqatdan ma'lum moslashuvchi harakatlar bilan birga bo'ladi, lekin bu harakatlarga borib yetmaydi. Agar tomoshabin sahnadan o'girilsa, ko'zini yumadi, quloqini berkitadi, u sahnada nima bo'layotganiga diqqat qilolmaydi. Sahnaga qarash va

³ Bleyxer V.M. , Burlachuk L.F. Psixologicheskaya diagnostika intellekta i lichnosti. K., 1978.

⁴ Volkov B.S. Vozrastnaya psixologiya. V 2-x ch. Ucheb. posobie dlya Vuzov, spes. OPD.F.01-Psixologiya / Pod red. B.S.Volkova. – M.: VLADOS, 2005. Ch.2. – 343 s.

eshitish uchun boshqa hamma narsalardan chalg'ish kerak va idrokni sahnada bo'layotgan hodisalarga qaratish lozim. qarab turib ko'rmaslik, tinglab turib eshitmaslik mumkin. Diqqat shundan iboratki, u nimaga qaratilgan bo'lsa uni ko'rish demakdir. Yug'oridagi mulohazalardan kelib chiqqan holda N.F.Dobrinin diqqatni kishi psixik faoliyatini biron-bir ob'ektga yo'naltirish va to'plash bilan boshqa ob'ektlardan chalg'ish orqali tushuntiradi.

Diqqat psixik faoliyatning qandaydir ob'ektga yo'nalishi va to'planishi orqali o'rganishni qator mualliflar tanqid qiladilar. Ana shulardan biri S.L.Rubinshteyndir. S.L.Rubinshteyn diqqatni alohida mazmunga ega emasligiga qo'shiladi, lekin uning guvohlik berishicha, diqqatni biror ob'ektga tanlab yo'nalishi uning fenomenologik xarakteridir. Bunday fenomenologik tavsifnomada ham diqqatning tabiati va xususiyatlari ochilmay qolaverar ekan.

Psixolog G.S.Bakradze diqqatning ob'ektda to'planishi faoliyatning roli haqida qiziqarli ilmiy tekshirish tajribasini o'tkazgan. Agarda diqqatni zaifligini tekshiruvchi o'z vaqtida payqab, unga nisbatan qandaydir muskul harakatini amalga oshirsa, u yana tiklanadi. Bulardan tashqari diqqat barqarorligini faoliyatning xarakteriga, shaxsning o'ziga bog'liqligi bir qancha psixologlar tomonidan isbotlangan.

Jumladan, A.P.Gazova⁵ diqqatning bo'linuvchanligini ko'p stanokda ishlovchi to'quvchilarda o'rganib, juda qimmatli materiallarni yig'adi. Uning fikricha, diqqat bu kasbdagi odamlarda ixtiyorsiz va ixtiyoriy muvozanatlashgan bo'lishi mumkin. Bir necha stanokda ishlash malakalari hosil bo'lishi natijasida bularda ixtiyoriy muvozanatlashgan diqqat turi vujudga keladi.

Diqqatning bo'linuvchanligi ustida olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ikkita yoki uchta ishni birdaniga bajarish mumkin, bunda I.P.Pavlov⁶ ko'rsatganidek, ulardan biri tanish (ishlash oldin bajarilganligini eslatuvchi) va bosh miya yarim sharlar po'stlog'ida "navbatchi punktlar" mavjud bo'lsa amalga oshiriladi. Ikkita faoliyatni bir davrning o'zida bajarish uchun faoliyatning biri diqqatni talab qilmaydigan yoki avtomatlashgan bo'lishi talab qilinadi. Kishida bunday imkoniyat faqat mashq qilish orqaligina yuzaga kelishi mumkin.

Sobiq sovet psixologiyasi namoyondalari, jumladan N.F.Dobrinin⁷ o'zi va shogirdlari o'tkazgan tekshirishlariga asoslanib, bunday tipologiya diqqatning mohiyatini ochishga yetarli emas deb hisoblaydi. Turmushda shunday odamlar uchraydiki, ular ob'ektni ko'p, ham aniq idrok qila oladilar. Yana shunday toifadagi kishilar mavjudki, ular narsalarni ham kam, ham noaniq idrok qiladilar, o'zlaridan ko'p narsalarni qo'shib yuboradilar.

Tadqiqotchi Ye.B.Pirogova⁸ o'quvchilarda eshitish va ko'rish diqqatini o'rganib, eshitish diqqatining ko'lami ko'rish diqqatidan bir necha bor kichikligini ta'kidlab o'tadi. Diqqat muammosini o'rganuvchi olimlar uning boshqa psixik jarayonlar bilan bog'liqligi va roli masalalarini o'rganganlar. Jumladan, N.N.Lange, A.R.Luriya va boshqalarning tadqiqotlarida ko'rishimiz mumkin.

N.N.Lange⁹ diqqatning iroda, reflektiv, instinktiv, perseptiv holatlar bilan bog'liqligini o'zining "Irodaviy diqqat nazariyasi" asarida ko'rsatib beradi. A.R.Luriyaning fikricha, kichik

⁵ Diagnostika psixicheskogo razvitiya. Praga, 1978.

⁶ Djems Uil'yam. Psixologiya: (perevod) pod.red. L.A.Petrovskoy. M: Pedagogika, 1998. – 367s

⁸ Vasil'ev I.A.,Magomed-Eminov M.SH. Motivasiya i kontrol' za deystviem. –M.: Izd-vo MGU, 1998. –143 s.

⁹ Djems Uil'yam. Psixologiya: (perevod) pod.red. L.A.Petrovskoy. M: Pedagogika, 1998. – 367s.

yoshdagi bolalarda diqqatning bu holatini ko'rish oson. Birinchi bosqichda u beqarorligi va ko'lamining torligi uchun qo'zg'atuvchilar qurshovidagi diqqat bo'lolmaydi.

Uluq rus pedagogi K.D.Ushinskiy¹⁰ ishlarida diqqat to'g'risida bir qator fikrlar aytilgan. Diqqat ob'ektni to'la va aniq idrok qilish qobiliyatiga ega. Ziyraklikning qator sabablariga oldin idrok qilingan ob'ekt izlarining ahamiyatidan tashqari K.D. Ushinskiy "ta'sirotning kuchi va to'plangan aktlarni boshqara olishni ko'rsatadi". Bolaning rivojlanishi uchun diqqatini to'g'ri yo'naltira olish muhimligini ko'rsatib o'tadilar. Diqqatning to'laligi barqarorligini ta'minlovchi to'planishning psixologik mexanizmlarini muhokama qilish ham K.D.Ushinskiyning asarlarida uchraydi. U diqqatning asosiy omili irodaviy boshqarish deb hisoblaydi. Shuning uchun diqqatni maqsadga yo'naltirib, boshqara olish qiyin va murakkab jarayondir. K.D.Ushinskiyning ko'rsatishicha, kishi o'z hissiyotlarini diqqat orqali boshqaradi, bunda u ixtiyoriy yoki faol turlarga ajratadi. Uningcha, ixtiyoriy diqqat bizning tomonimizdan zo'r berish orqali o'ziga predmet tanlaydi. Ixtiyoriy diqqatni ob'ektivlashtirish faol xarakteridan biridir. Chunki u kishining o'zi orqali qo'zg'atiladi va qo'llaniladi.

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¹⁰ 24s. Dashkevich O.V. Emosional'naya deyatel'nost' v ekstremal'nix usloviyax: Avtoref dok dis. M. MGU, 1996

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